

Lost Information in Differential Equations and Link to Statistical Mechanics

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In (1), the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions are considered from the point of view of differential equations, specifically $dp/dx = p$ and $dp/dx = p$ power q , where $x = -e_i/T$. A differential equation is a mathematical entity with a mathematical solution which in general has nothing to do with statistical mechanics or probability. The question we investigate is: Why should an a priori differential equation be linked to statistical mechanics?

We suggest that $dp/dx = p$, as a math equation, represents lost or removed information because a power series of p in x usually has a different function representing its derivative. It is unusual to have dp/dx and p be the same function and so we argue that information is lost. This loss of information seems to be carried over into the argument x ($p(x)$), because, given the solution $p(x) = \exp(x)$, $\exp(x_1)\exp(x_2) = \exp(x_3)\exp(x_4)$ ((1a)) if $x_1+x_2=x_3+x_4$ ((1b)). Now these latter two equations only are relevant if they describe some kind of meaningful process or state. If, however, one considers x as a conserved quantity (as in ((1a))), then ((1b)) shows a loss of information if in fact $\exp(x_1)\exp(x_2)$ has any meaning. It does, however, have meaning in a two-body collision. Thus, we argue that certain differential equations represent a loss of information and that this loss of information may map to a physical situation in which this loss of information is actually associated with probability.

We show that from the two constraints $\sum \text{over } i \ p(x_i) = 1$ and $\sum \text{over } i \ x_i \ p(x_i) = E_{ave}$, one may obtain the differential equation described above if there exists a function $F(p(x_i)) = x_i$, whose changes in $p(x_i)$ as a function are represented by information from the constraints alone. This result is akin to a loss of information represented by ((1a)).

Differential Equation Approach to Statistical Mechanics

In (1), two statistical distributions, the Maxwell-Boltzmann (M|B) and Tsallis, are described as following from differential equations a priori. It is noted that the exponential (MB) function follows from:

$$dp/dx = p \quad ((2))$$

and (1) calls this "the most important characterization of the exponential function". The Tsallis distribution is then obtained from a "slightly nonlinear generalization" of this differential equation, namely:

$$dp/dx = p \text{ power } q \quad (3))$$

Given the a priori nature of these statements, we try to consider in this note, why a differential equation should contain the essence of statistical mechanics/probability theory, at least for two example distributions. After all, a differential equation is a math equation which at first seems to have nothing to do with probability and statistical mechanics.

The Notion of Loss of Information

We consider ((2)) and argue that this differential equation represents a loss of information regarding the function $p(x)$. In particular, if:

$$p(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n) x^n \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Then } dp/dx = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n (a_n) x^{n-1} \quad ((5))$$

In general, ((5)) should be a different function from ((4)). In ((2)) it is not and so we argue that a loss of functional information is present. This loss of functional information seems to be carried over into a loss of x information in the solution $p(x)$ if one considers ((1a))

$$p(x) = \exp(x) \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(x_1)\exp(x_2) = \exp(x_3)\exp(x_4) \quad \text{if} \quad x_1+x_2 = x_3+x_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad ((1b))$$

The above consideration only holds if one considers x to be a conserved quantity. In other words, a specific physical scenario is being created. If x is a conserved quantity and there is the possibility of two different x 's combining, then there is an equivalence between the product of $p(x_i)p(x_j)$ as long as $x_i+x_j = E$. In other words, there is a loss of information in x , but only at the sum level of x level. If this scheme, however, maps to a physical situation, then this lack of information or equivalence of $p(x_i)p(x_j)$ may give rise to probabilistic interpretation very similar to the notion of a uniform distribution.

In particular, with a uniform distribution (die or coin), there are various possible outcomes and one assigns the same weight or probability to each. In the case of e_i, e_j pairs, such that $e_i+e_j=E$, one assigns the same product weight $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ to each. Thus, this lack of information becomes a probabilistic scheme, in particular, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

The Notion of Constraints

In the above sections, we have considered a loss of information in x as being linked to a statistical situation, in particular, the MB distribution. Here, we examine the problem from the point of view of constraints and see how the differential equation dp/dx arises in this picture and how the constraint scenario is linked to a lack of information, namely $p(x_1)p(x_2)=p(x_3)p(x_4)$ if $x_1+x_2=x_3+x_4$.

One may consider the probabilistic problem with constraints:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n p(x_i)=1 \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n x_i p(x_i) = E \quad ((6b))$$

There are multiple $p(x_i)$ solutions to these two constraints. Imagine, for the sake of argument, that one wishes to construct a function of $p(x_i)$ which when varied with respect to the functional form of $p(x)$, represents no new information than that contained in the variation of $p(x_i)$ in the constraints ((6)).

We start with:

$h(p(x_i)) = x_i$ ((7)) and consider $G = \sum \text{over } i \ p(x_i) h(p(x_i))$ ((8)) to mimic ((6b))

Then: $dG = \sum \text{over } i \ p(x_i) dh/dp(x_i) dp(x_i) + h(p) p(x_i)$ ((7))

((7)) may then be compared with: $\sum \text{over } i \ dp(x_i) = 0$ and $\sum \text{over } i \ x_i dp(x_i) = 0$ ((8))

This leads to: $h(p) = x \rightarrow dh/dp dp/dx = 1$ and $p dh/dp = 1$ from which:

$dp/dx = p$ ((9)) arises.

Thus, the constraint approach leads to the differential equation ((2)) which is linked with a loss of information. One may ask: How does one see the loss of information in the above process? Consider:

$\sum \text{over } i, j \ (x_i + x_j) p(x_i)p(x_j) = 2E_{ave}$ ((9))

If one writes: $d \sum \text{over } i, j \ p(x_i)p(x_j) h(p(x_i)p(x_j))$, then:

$h[p(x_i)p(x_j)] = x_i + x_j = h(p(x_i)) + h(p(x_j))$ ((10))

In other words, for any $x_i + x_j = E$, $p(x_i)p(x_j) = \text{constant}$ and information is lost. This implies, as a possible solution, that:

$p(x_i)p(x_j) = p(x_1)p(x_2)$ if $x_1 + x_2 = E = x_i + x_j$

In other words, ((10)) suggests a power law distribution, i.e. base power $x = p(x)$.

To see this more clearly, consider:

$p(x+dx) \approx p(x) + dx dp/dx \approx p(x) \exp(dx)$ with a possible solution of $p(x) = \exp(x)$, i.e. a power law probability. The loss of information is then directly linked with conservation of x .

Tsallis Case

We now consider the Tsallis case. We have considered a constraint $\sum \text{over } i \ x_i p(x_i) = E_{ave}$, but one may consider more generally $\sum \text{over } i \ x_i p(x_i)$ power q . In the case of $q=1$, one obtains the MB result and so one may expect a loss of information in this approach as well. Using the constraint method outlined above, one has:

$h(p(x_i)) = x_i$ and p power $q \ dh/dp(x_i) = 1$ ((11))

From ((11)), one may obtain the Tsallis result:

$\ln_q(p) = h(p) = (1 - p \text{ power } 1-q) / (1-q)$ so that $h(p)$ for $q=1 = \ln(p)$ ((12))

In this case, it is not so obvious that information is lost, but $dp/dx = p^q$ for $q=1$ becomes the MB scenario, and in that case information is clearly lost and so one would anticipate information being lost in the p^q case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that differential equations may represent a loss of information mathematically. In particular, $dp/dx = p$ represents the loss of information of the p derivative with respect to x because under normal circumstances this should be a completely different function from p . The solution for p , $\exp(x)$, also represents information loss, but only when considered in terms of a product: $\exp(x_1)\exp(x_2) = \exp(x_3)\exp(x_4)$ if $x_1+x_2=x_3+x_4$. The latter equation is of the form of a conservation equation and so if one may find a physical reason for combining x_1 and x_2 in $\exp(x_1)\exp(x_2)$, then one sees that any x_i, x_j pair for which $x_i+x_j=x_1+x_2$ yield the same product $\exp(x_i)\exp(x_j)$. This then is also a loss of information. This loss must now be linked to the notion of probability, but this is readily done as $\exp(x_1)\exp(x_2)$ is of the form of an AND product from probability. Thus, conservation of x is key to the whole problem, but the differential equation losing information maps into a problem of 2-body interactions which only depend on the sum x_1+x_2 and not on the actual x_1 and x_2 for $p(x_1)p(x_2)$. This then leads to the MB distribution.

An alternative way of obtaining the differential equation is to consider the two constraints: $\sum p(x_i)=1$ and $\sum x_i p(x_i) = E_{ave}$ and to create $G=\sum p(x_i) h(p(x_i))$ such that $h(p(x_i)) = x_i$ and a variation of the functional form p is equivalent to its variation in the constraints. Then: $h(p(x)) = x \rightarrow dh/dp dp/dx = 1$ and $p dh/dp = 1 \rightarrow dp/dx = p$ which is the differential equation used in (1). Thus, a lack of information in a differential equation may map into a statistical distribution under certain circumstances. We argue that the key circumstance here is the notion of conservation of energy $x_1+x_2=x_3+x_4$ with the loss of information meaning that the physical system does not distinguish between the probability of collision of x_1, x_2 and x_3, x_4 . Given the notions above, one could modify $dp/dx = p^q$ to obtain the Tsallis distribution as done in (1). Alternatively, we point out that one may change the constraint: $\sum x_i p(x_i) = E_{ave}$ to $\sum x_i p(x_i)^q = E_{ave}$.

References

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